

THE IMPORTANCE OF MASTERING FOREIGN LANGUAGES BY YOUNG CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS

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Annotation: another aspect of the importance of memory in language learning is that it helps to quickly and easily assimilate the vocabulary of the language being studied. Only when a language learner is more familiar with a second language is he able to speak this language fluently. It is this memory that is incomparable for a language learner. Experiments conducted by researchers show that teaching special exercises for mastering a second language to children from four to ten years old gives a positive result. In addition, “the importance of the game in teaching a foreign language to children between the ages of three and six and seven is great, which is an easy way to achieve the knowledge, qualifications and skills required on the specified topic.

Keywords: interactive methods, tilde fluency, special exercises for mastering a second language.

By our wise people, a lot of works, Proverbs, phrases have been created. All these proverbs are based on events that have passed through their heads. The wisdom of the Wise was not mentioned in vain. The confiscation of the article has found that it is permissible to start with such a pur wisdom sentence. “Knowledge gained in youth is a pattern carved in stone.” In fact, a person does not at all remember what he learned at a young age.

All of the points mentioned above are related to the article I want to describe. Because learning a language is also learning, learning. According to statistical data identified by scientists, up to the age of 7, a person owns 70% of world knowledge [Blakemore and Frith, 2005]. Based on this idea, it can be said that when learning a foreign language, the chances of Small-year-old learners are wider. Because it is precisely this thing that the learners of this age are full of when they learn something, they pay all their attention, passion, interest. Also, considering that the most important tool in language learning is memory, “in younger learners, this tool, that is, memory, has not yet been occupied, quickly accepts what has been learned in its pure state and is firmly established.”

Another aspect of the importance of memory in language learning is that it helps to quickly and easily assimilate the vocabulary of the language being studied. Only when a language learner is familiar with more words in a second language can he speak this language fluently. It is this memory that is incomparable for a language learner.

Experiments conducted by researchers show that teaching special exercises for mastering a second language to children from four to ten years old gives a positive result. In addition, “the importance of play in teaching a foreign language to children between the ages of three and six and seven is significant, making it an easy way to achieve the knowledge, qualifications and skills required on a specified topic”. It is effective to explain topics to younger language learners in a playful way, in which students learn the language in an interactive way, through physical action. The approach, taking into account the individual characteristics of students: interests, physical, mental abilities, gives positive results. Based on research carried out in this area, “games intended for language learning are divided into 4 types: single or independent games; parallel Games;

games in cooperation and harmony”. Through the game, the reader not only learns the language, but also expands his worldview.

Knowledge of the basic methodological requirements for a modern foreign language lesson, the level of study of a foreign language by students of a particular class, their attitude to the subject of a foreign language will help to increase the effectiveness of the intended study from planning.

In high schools, students only have difficulty learning pronunciation. Including: almost all readers have difficulty learning the sounds [θ] and [ð]. The reason for this is the absence of the sounds of the tooth gap in the Uzbek language. The language of our children did not characterize the skill in the pronunciation of these sounds. since the English pronunciation of the sound [r] differs from the R in the Uzbek language, readers also have difficulty in the pronunciation of this sound. the pronunciation of the sounds [t, d] is not the same in both languages. Therefore, their pronunciation is also a challenge for some students. the sound [w] is also not available in Uzbek. Even when pronouncing this sound correctly, readers will have some difficulty. When pronouncing it, they confuse it with the Uzbek language [v]. In order to teach the correct pronunciation of the above sounds, the teacher must clearly explain to the children the location of the language as practically as possible, regularly check it through repetition exercises, and if each lesson pays special attention to the pronunciation of the students, the difficulties in these sounds will also be eliminated. In addition, the following situations also create phonetic difficulties for students:

- the fact that the letter e is not pronounced at the end of the word-apple, Pete;
- failure of the GH letter combination to be read in the middle of the word-eight, night;
- the fact that the letter k is not pronounced before n at the beginning of the word — knock, knee;
- a number of other difficulties can be observed.

Based on my experience, I can say that the difficulty inherent in most Uzbek readers is that they add the sound [ə] before suffixes in their pronunciation, when plural or tense-forming suffixes are added: books [this], happened [hæpəd].

Apparently, by adding such an unnecessary sound, they are also changing the position of the word accent. The fact that readers cannot read transcription is also a separate problem. Teaching the correct pronunciation of words should also be taught the signs that represent sounds. When speaking about the grammatical difficulties encountered in teaching English in high schools, it is permissible to say that students face many difficulties. When a person knows all the words in his language and does not know the connections between sentences and words, he finds it difficult to understand the content of speech. That is why it is so important to teach grammar to students in high schools. If the reader has not mastered grammatical skills well, he will not be able to correctly state his opinion. Has difficulty speaking, writing and translating.

Language grammar is a kind of complex system. That is why it is not so easy to master it. Schoolchildren are usually faced with the following difficulties: the problem of articulation. This can even be said to be the biggest problem in grammar learning. When we talked to many English language learners, almost all of them said that in their mastery of English grammar, mainly articles and tenses cause difficulties. Indeed, since the Uzbek language does not have exactly the articl Word series, they have difficulty applying and translating it. Artikl need to memorize the rules. However, only exceptional cases in the rules make it difficult for learners, especially those of school age, to master it. When the translation is taught more

precisely, students do not have much difficulty in applying the article. For example: an ambiguous artikl can be taught that one is somehow translated as the same, while the exact artikl is. In a word, the use cases of artikl can be explained to children over and over again using examples, reducing and eliminating the difficulties in mastering this auxiliary word category in English. Another of the difficulties in mastering English grammar is prepositions.

In the Uzbek language, prepositions are represented by adverbial adverbs. In English, however, the adverbial adverbs are expressed through prepositions. In particular, the place-time agreement in the Uzbek language can be expressed in English with prepositions in, on, at. For example:

in-in January, in 2015, in a week;
an-an Mandey, an January 15, an birthday;
at-at the weekend, at 10 o'clock.

The suffix of the arrival of the place moment, when the place denotes the place, we also use the prepositions above in English. For example:

in-Uzbekistan, in Madrid, in aur week;
an, - An the sofa, an the table;
at-at the station, at school.

The fact that the word order in English and Uzbek is not similar. It is known that in English the word order is strict, in most cases the word darak always has at the beginning of the sentence and the participle comes from behind. And in Uzbek, the meaning does not change even if we replace the parts of speech. And in translation, readers have difficulties.

According to Methodists, when teaching English grammar, it is necessary, first of all, to correctly select the grammar minimum and take into account the peculiarities of English grammar. The specific difficulties and features of the grmmatics of the English language are the following: the presence of incorrect verbs in the English language, the strictness of the construction of a sentence in the English language, the abundance of articulations, prepositions and tenses in the English language. Similar features distinguish English grammar from Uzbek grammar. J.According to jalalov, we can mainly use two ways to teach grammar to students:

1. Inductive.
2. Didactic.

In the inductive method, students are first given an example after the rule. In the didactic method, however, an example is first followed by a rule. When teaching English to school-age children, we must first pay attention to colorfulness for children. We can also teach English grammar based on pictures or through songs and poems. Among the problems observed in schools, the student also has aspects such as passivity, boredom, inability to concentrate in relation to the lesson. As for the lexical difficulties in teaching English, they are as follows: almost all words in English mean different meanings. That is, a word means suddenly in love. M.Norova noted that one word in English gives a maximum of 23 meanings. The fact that a certain part of the English vocabulary came from other languages; it is natural that the English language is rich in idioms, as well as a number of others, in conclusion, to have difficulties in learning a foreign language, of course. It is important for teachers to track where students are experiencing difficulties and find ways to overcome it,

creating relief for students. After all, difficulties in mastering language materials prevent them from mastering skills in all types of speech activities

Proof of this is the continuous training of English language classes in the first classes of schools of general education, as well as in preschool educational organizations, as work on further improvement of the system of foreign language learning and the implementation of this decision. Learning, Mastering the language is closely related to the age periods of a person.

For example, children learn the language quickly and easily compared to older people. When mastering a foreign language, sounds are also pronounced more correctly and clearly than in adults.

As a reason for children to quickly learn a foreign language, the following can be listed:

- the strength of mechanical memory;
- an excess of time than an adult;
- the fact that imitation is strong in children;
- be more sociable;
- the presence of comrades in another nation.

The role of the game in the development of skills of small-age language learners, such as listening and understanding, expressing their opinion, is incomparable. The organization of games in connection with real realities is effective, and the linguist is more interested in events and phenomena that occur in everyday life. They react based on their worldview and interests.

People who have slogged the wisdom "it's too early to get knowledge-no later" are constantly in search. In each area seek to try themselves. Language learning is also not being left out of their perspective. These older learners are also doing well in language learning. But compared to younger learners, these have less chance levels. In our country today, great opportunities for language learning are being created. It was on this topic that a number of decrees and resolutions were published by our president. Many programs designed to teach language have been introduced in the media. All this further increases the passion of learners for mastering a foreign language and creates enough comfort. One drawback of older learners is that they express their speech without paying attention to the grammatical structure of sentences in order to enter into communication faster. Small-age learners carry out language mastering step by step, while in older adults this condition is rarely observed. They prefer to memorize more complex compound words. It is thought that with this we will beautifully outline their speech. But they do not think about the fact that they can face errors associated with simple words. Such mistakes, despite being simple, trivial, can put an individual in uncomfortable situations in some situations. The above examples show the shortcomings of adult learners.

In conclusion, it is worth saying that whether a person is young, older, has devoted himself to science, to the study of World Knowledge, his soul will certainly be filled with an increase. And the shortcomings of a person gradually disappear, he himself strives for heights. "People also stop thinking by the fact that they stop reading." So it turns out that science is of great importance when we become human and remain human. "Seek knowledge from the cradle to the grave." It is imperative that we all take this phrase as a slogan for ourselves, not stop searching.

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